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Mechanical Properties of 3D Cross Chiral Structures via Selective Laser Sintering

Wang Q.S., Lu Z.X., Yang Z.Y.

Institute of Solid Mechanics, Beihang University (BUAA), China

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Outline

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- 2 Materials and Methodology
 - ▣ Material design and fabrication
 - ▣ Experimental procedures
 - ▣ Numerical simulations
- 3 Mechanical Responses
- 4 Theoretical Analysis
- 5 Conclusions

Introduction

Alderson A, Chem. Industry, 1999
 Alderson A, et al. Compos. Sci. Technol. 2010

Special properties

- Excellent shear stiffness
- High fracture toughness
- **Energy absorption ability**
- High indentation resistance
- Synclastic curvature

Kolken, H. M. A. RSC Adv. 2017
 Evans, K. E. and Alderson, A. Adv. Mater. 2000

Application : Protective devices

- Defense field:
 - body armors
 - blast-protective deflector
- Automotive:
 - tires, bumper
- Sports field :
 - shoes, pads, gloves,
 - helmets and mats

Ju, J. et al. Compos. Struct. 2012
 Ma, Z. et al. U. S. Patent 2013
 Wang, C. Y. et al. Compos. Part B 2018

Ren X, et al. Smart Mater. Struct. 2018a, 2018b
 Smardzewski J, et al. Forest Wood Technol. 2011
 Sanami, M. et al. Procedia Eng. 2014

Introduction

Designs

Lakes R. Sci. 1987

Cabras, L. et al. J. Mech. Phys. Solids 2016

Ha, C. S. Phys. Status Solidi B 2016

Duan, S. et al. J. Mech. Phys. Solids 2018

Experimental research

Babaei, S. Adv. Mater. 2013

Yuan, S. et al. Mater. Des. 2017

Ren, X. Mater. Des. 2018

Shen, J. Phys. Status Solidi B 2014

Introduction

3D auxetic lattices

Fu M. et al. *Compos. Struct.* 2017
 Li, T. et al. *Sci. Rep.* 2017
 Wang, F. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 2018
 Bückmann, T. et al. *Adv. Mater.* 2012

Elastic and Physical Properties

Bückmann, T. et al. *New J. Phys.* 2014

Fu, M. et al. *Compos. Sci. Tech.* 2018
 Wu, W. et al. *Sci. Rep.* 2018

Wormser, M. *Appl. Phys. A* 2017

Mechanical Responses

Yang, L. et al. *Mater. Sci. Eng.* 2012
 Yang, L. et al. *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 2015

Chang, Q. L. et al. *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 2018
 Zong, H. *Mater. Des.* 2018

Warmuth F. et al. *Smart Mater. Struct.* 2016

Materials and Methodology

3D cross chiral structures (CCS)

Relative density:
$$\rho_r = \frac{(4l \cos \theta - 2t \cos \theta - t)t^2}{l^3 \cos^4 \theta}$$

Discussion of size effect

Design parameters for CCS

Model	θ	t/mm	$L \times W \times H / \text{mm}^3$	$\rho_r / \%$
CCS-1	10°	1	50.5 × 50.5 × 49.5	5.43
CCS-2	20°	1	50.5 × 50.5 × 49.5	5.71
CCS-3	30°	1	50.5 × 50.5 × 49.5	6.22

Materials and Methodology

Selective Laser Sintering (SLS)
Material: polyamide 12 (PA12) powder (size 20~40 μm)

Yuan, S. et al. Composites Part A 2018

Samples of CCS

Experimental procedures

- Testing machine: Instron 5565
- The velocity of the hard striker: 6.73% per second
- Experiment temperature: 16~20°C
- The Poisson's ratios are obtained with the help of Digital Image Correlation Method Commercial Software VIC-2D™ System

Materials and Methodology

Numerical model and Boundary conditions

Constitutive model for the component material

Numerical simulations

- Commercial Software ABAQUS:
Explicit Module
- The compressive velocity:
About 101% per second
- Element type:
C3D8R elements
- The contact interaction property:
Normal behavior: "Hard" contact
Tangential behavior: friction coefficient is about 0.1~0.3

Mechanical Responses

CCS-1

- Three failure modes are observed:
 - I. Plastic yielding for the struts at the top and bottom layers
 - II. Elastic buckling for the whole structure
 - III. Plastic yielding for the struts caused by lateral deformation, which is induced by an additional bending moment

Mechanical Responses

CCS-2

- ❑ Three failure modes are also observed in the whole compressive process.
- ❑ The elastic and plastic regions become wider and stress-strain curves are not as sharp as those of CCS-1

Mechanical Responses

CCS-3

- ❑ Samples are compressed bending-dominated and only the first failure mode is observed in the whole compressive process.
- ❑ Contact occurs to prevent the fracture of struts, leading to a plateau region in stress-strain curves

Theoretical Analysis

Plastic yielding for the struts at the top and bottom layers

Force analysis of the representative unit in the top or bottom layers.

The fully plastic moment for a perfectly plastic beam

$$M_p = \frac{1}{4} \sigma_{ys} ct^2 \left(1 - \left(\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_{ys}} \right)^2 \right)$$

The compressive yield stress is established

$$\sigma_z = \frac{2t\sigma_{ys} \left(\sqrt{(l \sin \theta)^2 + (t \cos \theta)^2} \right) - l \sin \theta}{l^2 \sin^4 \theta}$$

Theoretical Analysis

Discussion:

- ◆ The good agreement are observed between the results from the FEM and experiments, which helps to verify the validity of the FEM.
- ◆ The theoretical predictions exhibit the same trend as the experimental results, but showing some deviations.

Possible reasons:

- I. The deformation of the strut is neglected before failure.
- II. Defects in the surface and inside of samples arising from the manufacturing process

Conclusions

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- Three typical failure modes of CCS are observed in the compressive process. With the θ increasing, the main deformation translates from one that is compression-dominated to one that is bending-dominated and more contact occurs, which results in a plateau region in stress-strain curves for CCS-3 eventually.
- FEM models established in this research can simulate the compression behaviors of CCS very well, and reveal the failure mechanisms in detail.
- The theoretical predictions show the same trend as the experimental results, where the yield stress decreases as θ increases.

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THANKS!

PHD candidate of Institute of Solid Mechanics

Beihang University (BUAA), Beijing, 100083, China

E-mail: wangqs@buaa.edu.cn

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